

Studies on the Co-ordination Chemistry of Rhenium: Part I. Methylation of Cyano-Rhenates (II)

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The paper describes the isolation and study of certain methylated products of Re(II)-cyano derivatives. Two apparently isomeric compounds of the composition $[(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_4 \text{Re}(\text{CN})_2]$ and the salts of the ion $[\text{Re}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{+2}$ were isolated. They are ordinarily quite stable compounds and resemble the corresponding Fe(II) compounds.

Isocyanide complexes of iron are well known and a large volume of work has been done by Hartley¹ and Hölzl² on the alkylation of the ferrocyanides. Parallelism of cyano compounds of Fe and Re has been established by Sen³ by the isolation and study of a number of hexacyano and pentacyanoaquo-rhenates in the bivalent and trivalent states and also by Sarkar and co-workers⁴. Attempts have been made by the present authors to examine this parallelism further, and the present communication describes the isolation and study of several rhenium isocyanide complexes through the alkylation of the above mentioned rhenium cyano compounds.

Methylation has been achieved by heating the silver salts of the cyano compounds with methyl iodide. Two apparently isomeric compounds with the same composition $[\text{Re}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_4(\text{CN})_2]$ and salts of ion $[\text{Re}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{+2}$ have been isolated from hexacyano and pentacyanoaquo-rhenates respectively. Other derivatives are under investigation.

The two dicyanotetramethylisocyanorhenium(II) compounds are analogous to the corresponding iron compounds (*loc. cit.*). One of them is a brown powder (form-A) and the second one is a white crystalline solid (form-B). Unlike other cyano derivatives, they are not hygroscopic. On heating they are decomposed with the evolution of carbilamine, the form A at a temperature of $\sim 205^\circ$ and the form B at $\sim 230^\circ$. Both the compounds are feebly paramagnetic, less than that corresponding to one unpaired electron. The effective moment for the form A is 0.45 and form B is 0.47 Bohr Magnetons at 297°K. The absorption spectra show a sharp maximum at 38460 cm^{-1} for both of the two forms ($\epsilon = 2.68 \times 10^3$ for A and 2.53×10^3 for B). They are soluble in water, methanol, ethanol etc., the B form being slightly less soluble. The difference of the two forms lies in the insolubility of the form A in acetonitrile in which the second form is freely soluble. Dilute aqueous solution of B is very little conducting ($\mu = 30 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$) while, the form A behaves as a uni-univalent electrolyte ($\mu = 120 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$). The reactions of the two forms with metal ions are different in aqueous

1. E. G. J. Hartley, *J. Chem. Soc.* (London), 1910, **97**, 1066; 1912, **101**, 705; 1913, **103**, 1195.
2. F. Hölzl, *Monatsh.*, 1927, **48**, 71.
3. S. Sen, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1962, **315**, 315; 1965, **340**, 82.
4. B. K. Sen and P. B. Sarkar, *Science and Culture*, 1961, **27**, 404; 1961, **27**, 588; 1962, **28**, 290.

solution, the most important being that with ferric chloride which distinguishes them from the normal cyano compounds and also from each other. The form A gives a transient blue colouration changing to amethyst violet while the B-form gives red colour. Some other reactions are given in table I.

TABLE I

Cations	A [(CH ₃ CN) ₄ Re (CN) ₂]	B [(CH ₃ CN) ₄ Re (CN) ₂]
Ag ⁺	Pale yellow ppt.	White ppt.
Hg ⁺⁺	Pale yellow ppt. turning to brown on standing	Pale yellow ppt.
Cu ⁺⁺	Brown ppt.	No. ppt. or colouration.

Fe⁺⁺, Pb⁺⁺, Zn⁺⁺, Co⁺⁺ and Ba⁺⁺ give no ppt. or colouration with either of the compounds.

Pentamethylisocyanoaquorhenium(II)iodide is a dark red crystalline solid soluble in ethanol, methanol, chloroform, acetone and slightly in ether and water. It melts sharply at 82° without decomposition. The corresponding nitrate is a dark brown solid, highly soluble in water, alcohols, but insoluble in acetone, chloroform and ether. The iodide forms a silver iodide adduct with four molecules of AgI and this is a brown crystalline solid. Reactions of the nitrate with some anions are given in table-II.

TABLE II

Anions	...	[(CH ₃ CN) ₅ Re (H ₂ O)] (NO ₃) ₂
PtCl ₆ ⁼	...	Brownish black ppt.
Hg I ₄ ⁼	...	Brown ppt.
I ⁻	...	Reddish brown ppt.
ClO ₄ ⁻	...	-do-

All the methylated compounds are stable in the solid state in acidic solution and in organic solvents. Aqueous solution decomposes slowly with the liberation of carbonylamine and alkali brings about the decomposition very quickly.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium pentacyanoaquorhenate (II) and sodium hexacyanorhenate (II) were prepared by the methods described by Sen (loc. cit.), potassium perrhenate (Johnson-Matthey) being used as the starting material. The magnetic moment was determined by a Guoy balance. The absorption spectra were recorded with a Hilger Uvispek Spectrophotometer. Conductivity measurements were done with a Philips conductivity bridge in triple distilled water.

Methods of analysis: Rhenium was estimated by electrodeposition⁵ after decomposing the compounds with peroxide fusion and separating rhenium either by precipitating it as Re₂S₇ or by removing other elements by suitable precipitants. Carbon and hydrogen was estimated by micro combustion and nitrogen by micro-Duma's method. Iodine was determined gravimetrically as AgI. In the AgI-adduct total iodide was determined by the reaction with excess AgNO₃ in dilute nitric acid medium and the free AgI was determined by digesting the compound with dilute nitric acid.

5. B. K. Sen and P. Bandyopadhyay, *This Journal*, 1963, **40**, 709.

Preparation of tetramethylisocyano compounds: Freshly precipitated and dried (in vacuum over concentrated sulphuric acid) silver salt $\text{Ag}_4 \text{Re}(\text{CN})_6$ was heated in a sealed tube with a five fold excess of methyl iodide in methanol medium for six hr. on a water-bath maintained at 85° . After the reaction was over, it was filtered and washed with methanol. The combined filtrate was concentrated and excess of ether was added to the solution. An oil was separated which finally solidified to a brown powder. This was filtered and washed with methanol ether mixture. This was redissolved in methanol, filtered and evaporated in vacuum to a brown powder (product-A). The ethereal solution was concentrated and acetone was added to it when white crystals separated. These are filtered and washed with acetone-ether and recrystallised from methanol (product-B).

Analysis of product A gives Re 46.0, C 28.5, H 2.94, N 20.9 per cent and the product B gives Re 46.9, C 28.9, H 2.91, N 21.2 percent. The formula $[(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_4\text{Re}(\text{CN})_2]$ requires Re 46.3, C 29.8, H 2.98, N 20.9 per cent.

Preparation of pentamethylisocyano compounds: Freshly precipitated and dried $\text{Ag}_3(\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5\text{H}_2\text{O})$ was heated with methyl iodide just as above. On completion of the reaction a deep red liquid was obtained along with a brown crystalline powder. The solid was filtered and washed with methanol. This product has the composition $[(\text{Re}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_5\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{I}_2, 4 \text{AgI}]$ [Found N 4.57, I (total) 46.8, free AgI 59.2 per cent. Required N 4.37, I (total) 47.5, free AgI 58.6 per cent]. On warming with calculated quantity of silver nitrate solution containing a few drops of dilute nitric acid, this was quantitatively converted to silver iodide and a soluble nitrate. The solution was filtered and concentrated in vacuum. Acetone was added to it when a dark brown solid was precipitated. This was filtered and washed with acetone. The air dried compound is of the composition $[\text{Re}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_5\text{H}_2\text{O}](\text{NO}_3)_2$ (Found: Re 35.3, N 18.2 per cent. Required Re 34.9, N 18.4 per cent). The red methanolic liquid was evaporated to remove the excess of methyl iodide, the solid was redissolved in acetone and concentrated to crystallisation. Dark red crystals were obtained, which were filtered and washed with carbon tetrachloride to remove any free iodine. The composition was found to be $[\text{Re}(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_5\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{I}_2$ (Found: Re 28.4, N 10.8, I 38.5 per cent. Required: Re 28.1, N 10.6, I 38.3 per cent). The nitrate described before could also be prepared by the double decomposition of this iodide with silver nitrate, firstly removing the insoluble AgI and then precipitating the compound by acetone. The methylation reaction is presumed to proceed in the following manner,

Further work including the characterisation of the two forms of dicyanotetramethylisocyano rhenium (II) are in progress and these will be published later.

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